

Kinetics and Mechanism of Parallel Reactions : Hydrolysis of Sec-Amyl Chloride in Neutral Medium

VIJAI SWAROOP, DHARAM PRAKASH* and RAKESH
KUMAR KHANNA

Directorate of Geology & Mining, U.P., 2-Way Road, (27/4,
Ram Mohan Rai Marg), Lucknow (U.P.), (India)

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It was earlier shown^{1,3-5,7,9,11-14} that few alkyl halides undergo the elimination reaction kinetically independent of simultaneous substitution in the alkaline medium. Recently, Swaroop and co-workers^{6,8} have studied the kinetic dependence of olefin elimination and substitution processes which occur simultaneously in the solvolysis of halides in the neutral medium. The present investigation mainly deals with the kinetic dependence of two simultaneous reactions, occurring in neutral hydrolysis of sec-amyl chloride. The hydrolysis of sec-amyl chloride have not been studied so far by any previous worker in any medium. Bimolecular substitution, bimolecular elimination and unimolecular substitution reactions generally take place simultaneously as observed in the hydrolysis of alkyl chlorides^{1,3} so far studied and thus information regarding the presence of simultaneously occurring unimolecular elimination reaction in the hydrolysis of alkyl chlorides has not been quoted in the literature so far. The present investigation provides full information about unimolecular substitution and elimination processes which occur simultaneously. Olefin elimination and simultaneous substitution reaction both followed first order with respect to the halide. Total first order rate constant has been split up into its constituents (Olefin elimination and substitution rate constants) by suitable measurement of olefin formed. The doubt, regarding the pertinent role of an alkali as a reactant in the reaction through unimolecular route, has been proved to be valid by calculating the extent of hydrolysis through unimolecular route in presence of some finite concentration of alkali. The present investigation also includes the effect of change in the composition of the medium on the rate of reactions, calculation of separate energies of activation in both processes, effect of salt on rate of reaction. In the present case, the unimolecular processes may take place through the scheme given by Moelwyn-Hughes and Fell².

Materials and Methods

Sec-amyl chloride (Fluka, 99%) was dried over anhydrous sodium carbonate and calcium chloride and thereafter fractionated. The fraction collected at 96°-97° (B.P.) was used for all kinetical measurements.

The value of first order rate constants was determined by estimating the acid produced as a result of hydrolysis sec-amyl chloride at various intervals of time and by employing the usual integrated formula for first order. The olefin was estimated by the following method. The sealed ampule containing 5 ml of the reaction mixture was first cooled and then broken by shaking under water 0° in an evacuated stoppered flask provided with an inlet and outlet tube, the former reaching to the bottom. The flask was kept at 50°-60° in a water bath and the whole amount of olefin produced was swept by passing a slow stream of nitrogen and bubbling the gas in a flask containing a known amount of bromine in carbon tetrachloride. The remaining bromine was estimated by titrating it against standard thiosulphate. The substitution product was identified as sec-amyl alcohol by the method described earlier^{3-5,11-14}.

Results and Discussion

The kinetic data are summarised in Tables 1-3. Table 1 includes the total first order rate constant obtained under various physical conditions, mentioned in columns 1, 2 and 3. The increase in the velocity of the unimolecular process on addition of water to the reaction mixture is in accordance with theory of solvent action¹¹ and the findings of Eliel and Ro¹⁰. The decrease in the rate of unimolecular process by an initial addition of potassium chloride may be ascribed due to the decrease in the nucleo-

TABLE 1—DIFFERENT RATE CONSTANTS OBTAINED FOR
THE NEUTRAL HYDROLYSIS OF SEC-AMYL CHLORIDE

k'_1 in min^{-1} . Limits of accuracy are $\pm 2.5\%$ or less unless otherwise stated.

Temperature (°C)	[EtOH - H ₂ O] (v/v%)	[KCl] × M	$k'_1 \times 10^{-4}$
[Sec-amyl Chloride] = $4.09 \times 10^{-2} M$			
70	80	—	8.16
"	75	—	12.02
"	70	—	15.89 ^a
"	65	—	17.93
"	60	—	20.58
"	55	—	28.64 ^a
"	50	—	37.57
"	45	—	48.11
"	40	—	56.19
[Sec-amyl Chloride] = $8.19 \times 10^{-2} M$			
"	60	0.25	18.41
"	"	0.50	16.10
"	"	0.75	14.32
"	"	1.00	12.88
"	"	1.25	9.93
"	"	1.50	7.79
"	"	1.75	5.63
"	"	2.00	3.20
75	"	—	32.26
70	"	—	20.61
65	"	—	12.39
60	"	—	7.63
55	"	—	4.45
50	"	—	2.45
45	"	—	1.48
40	"	—	0.85

^a → 3.2%.

* For correspondence

TABLE 2—UNIMOLECULAR SUBSTITUTION AND ELIMINATION RATE CONSTANTS AND THEIR SPLITTING

Exp.	Temp. (°C)	[EtOH-H ₂ O] (%v/v)	E ₁ (%)	SN ₁ (%)	$\frac{E_1}{SN_1 + E_1}$	$\frac{SN_1}{SN_1 + E_1}$	k' ₁ × 10 ⁻⁶ min ⁻¹	k' _{1E} × 10 ⁻⁶ min ⁻¹	k' _{1s} × 10 ⁻⁶ min ⁻¹
[Sec-amyl Chloride] = 8.19 × 10 ⁻² M									
1	75	60	4.72	95.28	0.0472	0.9528	32.26	1.52	30.74
2	70	"	4.36	95.64	0.0436	0.9564	20.61	0.90	19.71
3	65	"	3.93	96.07	0.0393	0.9607	12.39	0.49	11.90
4	60	"	3.51	96.49	0.0351	0.9649	7.63	0.27	7.36
[Sec-amyl Chloride] = 4.09 × 10 ⁻² M									
5	70	80	5.12	94.88	0.0512	0.9488	8.16	0.42	7.74
6	"	75	4.93	95.07	0.0493	0.9507	12.02	0.59	11.43
7	"	70	4.75	95.25	0.0475	0.9525	15.89	0.75	15.14
8	"	65	4.57	95.43	0.0457	0.9543	17.93	0.82	17.11
9	"	60	4.40	95.60	0.0440	0.9560	20.56	0.91	19.67
10	"	55	4.28	95.72	0.0428	0.9572	28.64	1.23	27.41
11	"	50	4.17	95.83	0.0417	0.9583	37.57	1.57	36.00
12	"	45	4.03	95.97	0.0403	0.9597	48.11	1.94	46.17
13	"	40	3.91	96.09	0.0391	0.9609	56.13	2.19	53.94

TABLE 3—COMPARISON OF TOTAL UNIMOLECULAR, UNIMOLECULAR SUBSTITUTION AND UNIMOLECULAR ELIMINATION RATE CONSTANTS, ENERGIES OF ACTIVATION, ENTROPIES OF ACTIVATION FOR THE HYDROLYSIS OF SEC-AMYL HALIDES

[EtOH-H ₂ O] = 60% (v/v)										
k' ₁ , k' _{1s} and k' _{1E} are in min ⁻¹ . (Temp. 60°), E, E _s , E _e are in K cal/mole and ΔS, ΔS _s and ΔS _e are in e.u.										
Sec-Amyl Halide	k', × 10 ⁶	k' _{1s} × 10 ⁶	k' _{1E} × 10 ⁶	E	E _s	E _e	ΔS	ΔS _s	ΔS _e	
Sec-Amyl Chloride	7.63	7.37	0.27	22.81	22.45	26.75	-23.84	-24.99	-18.61	
Sec-Amyl Bromide ^a	391.20	370.00	21.20	22.06	23.12	24.59	-18.28	-15.19	-16.44	
Sec-Amyl Iodide ^a	483.10	458.70	24.40	17.82	17.73	19.18	-30.48	-30.86	-32.38	

philic activity of water molecules associated with the increase of ionic strength on addition of salt¹⁵.

Table 2 summarises the results of 13 sets of experiment in order to obtain the fractions (data of columns 6 and 7) in which the total actual unimolecular reactions are partitioned to give elimination and substitution reactions respectively. The percentages of olefins (shown in column 4) obtained in unimolecular process are the average of at least three observations. The data in column 5 are obtained by subtraction of data in column 4 from 100. The terms E₁ and SN₁ stand for the reactions occurring through unimolecular elimination and unimolecular substitution processes respectively. The data in columns 2 and 3 indicates the experiments carried out at various temperatures and different compositions of alcohol-water mixtures.

Columns 6 and 7 of Table 2 contain the factors which, when multiplied into the total unimolecular rate constant (data of column 8 in Table 2) will give the rate constants for the two separate unimolecular elimination and substitution reactions (see columns 9 & 10 of Table 2) respectively. A perusal of Table 2 shows that unimolecular substitution is faster than unimolecular elimination which may be attributed to predominance of inductive effect (responsible for former) over electromeric effect (responsible for latter). No trace of olefinic products was found below 60° in unimolecular process.

Table 3 records the data for the comparison of rate constants, energies of activation and entropies

of activation of various unimolecular simultaneous substitution and elimination reactions of sec-amyl chloride, sec-amyl bromide and sec-amyl iodide under similar physical conditions. Columns 2, 3 and 4 show the total unimolecular rate constant, unimolecular substitution rate constant and unimolecular elimination rate constant. E, E_s and E_e in columns 5, 6 and 7 represents the values of energy of activation for total unimolecular, unimolecular substitution and unimolecular elimination respectively and ΔS, ΔS_s and ΔS_e in columns 8, 9 and 10 represents the corresponding values of entropy of activation.

Under the same physical conditions, the total unimolecular rate constants, unimolecular elimination rate constants for the sec-amyl halides show the following sequence: sec-amyl chloride < sec-amyl bromide < sec-amyl iodide; which shows the same trend as obtained with lower members of primary alkyl halides series¹⁶.

The greater value of energy of activation for unimolecular elimination reaction over unimolecular substitution reaction in the study of the hydrolysis of sec-amyl chloride may be due to the velocity of elimination process, (more than 3 times) rises more rapidly than velocity of substitution process (below than 3 times) by the rise of 10° of temperature. The same trend is obtained in the case of sec-amyl bromide and sec-amyl iodide.

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Simplified Derivation of an Equation for Electroviscous Effect

B. N. GHOSH

Department of Chemistry, University College of Science,
Calcutta-700 009

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It appears to the author that the reasoning on the basis of which Street' derived an equation for electroviscous effect requires modification. Introducing such modification in Street's reasoning as is considered necessary an equation for electroviscous effect may be deduced in the following way.

Let us consider a suspension containing per cubic centimeter N uncharged spherical particles, each of radius a . During flow in a capillary there is relative movement between the liquid and the uncharged particles and let v be the relative velocity of a particle with respect to the liquid and F_2 the force per particle necessary to maintain this relative velocity (v). Now suppose that each particle of the suspension ionises and acquires a charge Q . Then to maintain the same relative velocity (v) of the charged particles an extra force F_1 per particle is necessary to overcome the drag which the oppositely charged layers of liquid exert on the particle.

Hence the total force (F) necessary to maintain the relative velocity (v) of a charged particle during flow is

$$F = F_2 + F_1 \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

Let η and η_s denote respectively the viscosity of the same suspension when the particles are all uncharged and charged

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Then } \eta_s &= \frac{F}{6\pi a v} = \frac{F_2}{6\pi a v} + \frac{F_1}{6\pi a v} = \eta + \frac{QE}{6\pi a v} \quad \dots \quad (2) \\ &= \eta + \frac{NQ^2}{6\pi a K} \quad \dots \quad (2a) \end{aligned}$$

As has been shown by Street $F_1 = QE$ and $E = \frac{NQv}{K}$ where K is the specific conductivity of the suspension.

Now $Q^2 = (\zeta Da)^2$ and $N = \phi \frac{4}{3} \pi a^3$, where ζ is the zeta-potential, D the dielectric constant and ϕ the volume fraction.

Substituting these values of Q^2 and N in equation (2a) and dividing both sides by η_0 the viscosity of the dispersion medium, we get

$$\eta_s/\eta_0 = \eta/\eta_0 + \frac{\phi}{2\eta_0 a^2 K} \left(\frac{D\zeta}{2\pi} \right)^2 \quad \dots \quad (2b)$$

According to Einstein $\eta/\eta_0 = 1 + 2.5\phi$.

It is to be noted that in Einstein's equation ϕ has to be multiplied by 2.5. Therefore, ϕ in $\frac{\phi}{2\eta_0 a^2 K} \left(\frac{D\zeta}{2\pi} \right)^2$ is multiplied by 2.5 and equation (2b) is written as follows :

$$\eta_s/\eta_0 = 1 + 2.5\phi \left[1 + \frac{1}{2\eta_0 a^2 K} \left(\frac{D\zeta}{2\pi} \right)^2 \right] \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

The equation derived by Street' is as follows :

$$\begin{aligned} \eta_s/\eta &= 1 + 2.5\phi \left[1 + \frac{\phi}{2\eta a^2 K} \left(\frac{D\zeta}{2\pi} \right)^2 \right] \quad \dots \quad (4) \\ &= 1 + K_1 \phi + K_2 \phi^2 \quad \dots \quad (4a) \end{aligned}$$

where $K_1 = 2.5$ and $K_2 = \frac{K_1}{2\eta a^2 K} \left(\frac{D\zeta}{2\pi} \right)^2$.

It is to be noted that Street's equation (4) or (4a) contains a term involving ϕ^2 which does not occur